

Digitalization Development of Family Businesses in Thailand

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Abstract

In Thailand, family-owned businesses has been growing strongly and rapidly, collectively contributed about 28 trillion baht or 72% of total business value and over 50% of listed company are family-owned businesses or run by families. They embrace technology to ensure they can continue to serve the evolving needs of their colleagues, customers and family members focusing on value-add activities. With today's business ecosystem of continuous change and innovation, business will need to be able to adjust to new ideas and the next generation will be key driver to this success. As businesses around the world are transforming their organisations to be more digital while using data to tailor a customer-centric experience, Thai family businesses are failing to prioritise the digital transformation of their operations.

Only 27% of family-owned businesses view improving digital capabilities as a top priority, while 25% believe they have strong digital capabilities. But the development of digitalization of family businesses in Thailand is very important because it can determine the strength and success of these companies in the present world.

Research background:

The digital transformation of family businesses in Thailand is particularly interesting as it reflects their efforts to narrow the digital divide, which is crucial for their future socio-economic development.

Purpose of the article: The purpose of the paper is to determine the Digitalization Development of Family Businesses in Thailand.

Methods: To achieve this goal, an analysis was carried out on the level of digitization of family businesses in Thailand based on reports on digitization.

Findings & value added:

The results of this study contribute to the literature on the level of digitalization of family businesses in Thailand. They show the level of their digital technologies, digital skills and their use, and what are the strengths and weaknesses of their digital development strategy.

Keywords: family business in Thailand, digital transformation, development of digitalization.

1. Introduction

In most countries, family businesses are the basis of the economy. To survive in today's highly unpredictable economic environment, the family organization must be able to adapt quickly to many circumstances. A family business must take into account both internal and external factors in order to be able to compete with others in a dynamic market and cope with uncertainty. Family businesses in Thailand are growing rapidly and dynamically and are now the backbone of Thailand's economy. The total value of family businesses in Thailand in 2018 was THB 28 trillion, which accounted for about 72 percent of the total value of all businesses in Thailand. In addition, more than 50 percent of companies registered in SET in 2018 are family businesses that are managed by family members.

Business professionalization remains a key issue as family businesses around the world face complex challenges and uncertainties such as trade barriers, cyber-attacks, and raw material

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costs, which involves not only business and investment decisions, but also ownership issues and relationships between family members (Family-owned businesses: Leading in an evolving business ecosystem).

Technology is one of the most common thing that enterprise businesses have already implemented. Thailand government tries to shape Thai business to industry 4.0 (Danssen et al., 2020) which refers to advance technology, for example, advanced robots (RPA), internet of things (IoT), drone, quantum computing, nanotechnology, 3D printing, big data, artificial intelligence (AI), cloud computing, augmented reality and edge computing.

A major problem for family businesses is a lack of innovation and resources (Miller et al., 2014). A family business should be aware of digitalization, which can disrupt the company's operations. Digitalization is the process of using digital technology to change the business process (ProcurementIQ, 2017).

To succeed in this era, a family business should think about the overall business strategy, social impact, and how technology works. This document recommends that family businesses use Thailand 4.0 as a priority, improve their operations, and distribute benefits to society. One of the new approaches is digital technology, which covers a wide range of three terminals, including digitalization, digitization, and digital transformation.

Digitization is the process of converting analog formats (i.e., documents, microfilm, photos, emails) into digital format (Lee, 2014). Digital format terms can refer to scanned documents, scanned photos, files, or emails. Digitization also involves the process of using a computer system to store data in a digital format, for example, locating data, recording health.

Digital transformation is the process of using digital technologies to modify or create new business processes and business culture to meet changing customer needs.

Digitalization, digitization and digital transformation are often included in the process of improvement and adaptation to existing businesses. Additionally, designing a new way to add value to products and services can help a family business run more smoothly and efficiently. Digitalization is also affecting external parties, helping all processes that use computer technology to transform and improve efficiency.

2. Literature review

2.1. Digital economy

The beginning of the 21st century is also the beginning of the fourth industrial revolution, in which digital transformation plays a key role. Its essence is the digital form of information. Digital text and image content can be quickly shared and processed from different angles thanks to technical means and their software. Activities in the digital reality result in both better access to knowledge and, moreover, the possibility of creating new knowledge, which is of particular importance today. Digitization with the use of appropriate hardware and software can contribute to the creation of many new technical or organizational solutions.

Digital economy – is a new type of economy that has been created in recent years based on the use of the Internet. Digitization processes are becoming universal and global, affecting not only some companies or selected sectors, but the entire society, the entire economy and connections between countries and societies in the world.

The modern global economy has been in the phase of digital transformation for several years. Changes are occurring at a rapid pace and have a significant impact on global economic processes. The digital economy is a consequence of technological development. On the other hand, the development of ICT technologies should be considered one of the most important

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factors influencing the way modern business operates in the world. Under the influence of progressive digitization, companies using new business models are increasingly competing on the market. Digitalisation involves cross-border flows, is common in the financial world and reaches public administrations, which create, among other things, smart cities. The digitalisation of the economy and society is one of the most dynamic changes, which opens up new opportunities for productivity growth (Boratyńska, Cieślik, Kacperska, Łukasiewicz, Milewska, 2021)

The particular importance, in some cases, is the disruptive nature of the changes taking place, bringing different values for market entities and consumers. Digitization, as a continuous process of convergence of the real and virtual worlds, is becoming the main engine of innovation and change in most sectors of the economy, local government units and public administration. According to Pieriegud, the key factors of the development of the digital economy are: the Internet of Things (IoT) and the Internet of Everything (IoE), hyperconnectivity, cloud computing, Big Data Analytics (BDA) and Big Data-as-a-Service (BDaaS), automation and robotisation, multi-channel and omni-channel models of distribution of products and services. (Boratyńska, Cieślik, Kacperska, Łukasiewicz, Milewska, 2021)

In order to meet these challenges, both individual enterprises and entire sectors, public administration, society, as well as national economies, must carry out the so-called digital transformation. Digitization also brings uncertainty, risk and various types of opportunities and threats related to, m.in social effects of automation and robotization of processes in the economy and public administration or broadly understood security. (Boratyńska, Cieślik, Kacperska, Łukasiewicz, Milewska, 2021).

Every family business must maintain its market share in a sustainable manner. Technology is one of the key factors that effectively drive businesses. Every family business must also have its platform to manage and maintain the business by bringing technology to the business. According to KPMG research (Wu Hong, 2017), as shown in Figure 1, digitalization is the main challenge for family businesses (about 64 percent). Digitization is a tool that can determine the strength of companies in this era. This can be seen in the example of successful companies that have fully integrated digitalization into their companies. The barriers of family businesses that abandon operations due to digitalization are formalization, an overly strong mental model, emotions about things, limited resources, and politics in family businesses – Figure 1 (Hunger and Hunger, 2017).

Figure 1: Main challenges for a family business (Hunger and Hunger, 2017).

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2.2 Thailand 4.0: The Evolution of the Thai Economy

The evolution of Industry 4.0 is the fourth of the changes in the process and system of the technology industry (Howard, 2018). Industry 4.0 is the integration of production by connecting everything via an internet connection and communication in every production process. The production process includes raw material, machines, tools, equipment, automation and robot. The relationship between Industry 4.0 and the consumer will allow for the production of a variety of products that meet the needs of customers. When it comes to a family business, each customer will have specific needs that are likely to adapt to their needs. On the other hand, mass customers are served by a large company.

Thailand 4.0 is one of the models of the evolution of the Thai economy (Jones and Pimdee, 2017). The Thai government is creating a model for economic development by transforming the production structure and the basis of Thai people's well-being. The number 4.0 indicates the level of economic development in Thailand. Thailand's economy was developed between 1.0 and 3.0. In addition, the Thai government has announced policies to bring Thailand's economy to full integration with 4.0 (Wiboonyasake, 2018). This policy is designed to create new business growth, including family businesses, enabling business owners to earn higher incomes, reduce technology imports, and create a balance by switching from goods to innovative products. Creativity Innovation, technology, research and development will help increase the advantage of these organizations to become more competitive.

Digitalization is part of Thailand 4.0 to support business processes and activities. Thailand 4.0 has three main objectives: to make Thailand a rich, stable and sustainable country, to drive the economy through innovation, technology and creativity, to create synergies of all sectors in line with the policy that connects with a network of business alliances.

For the implementation plan to be successful, the government will strengthen an approach that focuses on private sectors, people, banks, educational institutions, and research institutions. Thailand 4.0 is also being promoted among SMEs, start-ups, and family businesses in the country to join in the same direction (Louangrath, 2017). High-quality communication and telecommunications structures are supported so that Thais can access the internet as much as possible and all sectors can have a seamless connection. The goal of moving to newer technologies will be achieved through the cooperation of all industries, including SMEs, start-ups and family businesses. However, family businesses should use the right technology to grow faster without missing out on business opportunities. In addition, the owner should support every aspect of the training and skills of employees in thinking, analyzing and solving problems.

2.3 Digital transformation, digitalization and digitalization of family businesses

Today's world is increasingly connected through digital technologies, i.e. digital transformation, digitalization and digitization. A business that introduces digital technology into the economy can sustainably maintain its competitiveness in the market. Digital transformation is the creation of a digital business that aims to introduce technology to multiple channels within a company. This may result in a change in the form of the business transaction to a new market or a new target (Ashwell, 2017). Digital transformation is an innovation that connects data to people. It allows people to interact with technology. A family business needs to adapt its digital transformation process to recognize customer behavior, which is always changing. However, digital transformation cannot progress without the process of digitization.

In line with Gartner's business model focused on six combinations (ingenuity, create,

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engage, offer, monetize, and adapt), it was recommended that family businesses increase their use of technology and digitalization in transacting to improve business performance (Waller & Aron, 2014). The skills of the owner of a family business are also essential. The owner should have digital leadership to support the team and the company.

People accept that the Internet of Things (IoT) is widely used in daily life, such as drone, smart light switch, and mobile robot (Patel et al., 2016; Riahi, 2018). Most large companies continue to benefit from digitization and understanding their competitive advantage. Digital transformations are all about digital technology, people, data and interrelationships. The digital process requires technology that makes it easier to collect, discover, store, share, use, and secure data (Ashwell, 2017). Data mining and analysis also provide interconnections between data and data to see a pattern that we can forecast in the future.

Digitization is one of the main directions of Thailand's 4.0 policy. It will drive the economy to create prosperity, security, and sustainable development of the country in the long run. Digitalisation can help a company to streamline and transform business transactions, business functions and business models by using digital technology in knowledge or activities that can constitute a digital environment (Anchalikasite, 2017).

Allocating a budget to support technology in a family business is also key to leading the company towards digitalization. Enabling the budget to stimulate business innovation will help the company compete in the market. Most innovations in family businesses can allow their companies to increase their income. According to Deloitte research (Khalid et al., 2017), an investment in today's innovations can become tomorrow's operating expense. In terms of the report, companies invested 16 percent in business innovation, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Allocation of technology budgets (Khalid et al., 2017).

Digitalization is a very important element, as most family businesses are still unable to reach the next level of digital maturity in their operations. Digitalization is rapidly changing the market, customer attitudes and expectations. Disruption forces new technology to contribute to business growth faster, so it is necessary to start digitization (Lee, 2014). Digitalization is a megatrend that consequently affects family businesses.

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Figure 3: Digitalization framework (Waller and Aron, 2014),

According to the digitalization framework shown in Figure 3 (Waller and Aron, 2014), this study divides the success factors of companies into four categories as follows:

1) Focus on the business model.

Focusing on the business model means putting emphasis on value growth (Vermeulen, 2018); Business should focus on people, not just one customer or one employee. The concept is to enable a compromise between knowledge and innovative ideas. The opportunity here is not about imitation, but about creating value that supports the third party. This factor will allow you to create a new business idea in a different dimension.

2) Digital leadership opportunities

A leader or owner should think about the organization in a new way, adapted to the modern economy. In addition, the owner should think about a platform that will support all employees in the family business. In digital transformation, the owner should think about the effects in the long term to build a new foundation for increasing the company's capabilities (El Sawy et al., 2016).

3) Collaborate with colleagues and external clients

According to Potter's opinion, a third party, which can be internal or external, will become part of the family business ecosystem to support the product and service along with the business model (Potter, 2018). To understand the business process that should fit into digitalization, a family business should understand the ecosystem and apply a method with a high level of management skills to a third party.

The result of business innovation and the creation of a new type of value. The last category is related to the result of business innovation that the family business has already built to transfer the new value to the customer and employee (Davila et al., 2014). The next standard innovation is to change technology or develop new technology. To change a new value, an organization should explain to a third party what the change of company entails. In addition, a

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family business should protect its value by increasing its value proposition by focusing on costs. A family business should combine added value to the product and service for the customer to enable them to see value as the default. According to the digitalization framework, digitization is more of a way to transform a business model than a way to store data and information (Waller & Aron, 2014). Communication and internal and external engagement to obtain information creates a new idea. The most important thing in this process is to change the owner's mindset to digital leadership. All of the above reasons are aimed at creating business innovation and creating a new kind of value for business and the community.

2.4 Business Innovation and Digitalization Framework

The business innovation process aims to combine the business model, communication and leadership of digitalization and digitalization activities. A family business should be agile and flexible in order to survive in a highly competitive market. The interplay between business innovation and digitalisation is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Digitalization framework (Waller and Aron, 2014).

According to the Business Innovation and Digitalization Framework, the four disciplines are considered to be the factors that a family business must follow if it wants to survive in the digital age. In this study, we will use these factors to determine the business.

1) Online Services

Nowadays, people can easily and quickly access different online media related to the internet. Internet use is considered the main activity in the daily lives of people who use social media, search for information, check email, watch TV, or listen to music. Many businesses are turning to e-commerce to reach more customers.

2) Online Community

Community is one of the most important factors influencing people in everyday life. In addition, the online community is also used in digital marketing, as most successful businesses use an online social media platform.

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3) Data Analytics

Since the advent of internet and mobile phone technologies, there has been a high demand for data. A large amount of data can contribute to achieving business growth that makes an organization aware that data is being sent every second. An organization must be able to track and collect various information that is beneficial to it. Information technology will have an impact on the global economy in the future. This data can be transformed into a digital data process that can be used with both internal processes and external entities.

Considering the above, the Business Innovation and Digitalization Framework is the primary framework for family businesses to determine their operations compared to the best practices of family businesses in Thailand.

Digital technology is one of the megatrends that will play an important role in driving business in the coming years. Only a few family businesses believe that their companies have a strategy in place to support digital change, and changing technology is a big challenge in leading family businesses to success.

Most current management strategies lack knowledge and understanding of digitalization. As a result, business adaptations of family businesses are slower than those of other businesses, which ultimately affects the competitiveness of the family business. The new generation of family business owners should start to see the importance of digital technology, learn more about digitalization, invest accordingly, and have the ability to use technology to benefit the organization. A first-generation owner of an organization should have good business consultants who will help them plan investments and develop their business in the future.

3. Research methodology

Research has shown that digital opportunities are still low in family businesses in Thailand. As companies around the world transform their organizations to become more digital while using data to tailor customer-centric experiences, Thai family businesses are not prioritizing the digital transformation of their operations. Only 27% of respondents in Thailand consider improving digital capabilities to be a top priority (44% globally), while 25% believe they have strong digital capabilities (42% globally) (<https://www.pwc.com/th/en/press-room/press-release/2023/press-release-01-06-23-en.html>)

4. Results

Research has shown that digital transformation must continue to be a priority for family businesses in Thailand.

Figure 5 is shown, that only 25% of Thai family businesses have strong digital capabilities, significantly lower than the global 42% (PwC's 11th Global Family Business Survey).

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%

Agreeing with statements

5. Discussion

There are three main components of the digital economy: networked society, the digital transformation and the data economy. The specificity of the digital economy results from the closely interrelated processes of dataification and networking. Both of these processes have been constantly changing dynamically in recent years, as a result of the implementation of new technologies for, collecting, processing, analyzing and using data. At the same time, processes based on artificial intelligence are developing, which enables personalization to the needs and expectations of individual recipients. A major problem for family businesses is a lack of innovation and resources. A family business should be aware of digitalization, which can disrupt the company's operations.

6. Conclusions

Companies around the world are accelerating digital transformation to streamline operations and use data to tailor customer-centric experiences. Thai family businesses understand the importance of digitizing their organization, but they still lack digital capabilities compared to their global counterparts.

One in four Thai family businesses surveyed say they are confident in their digital capabilities. After a closer look at the key priorities, only 27% of Thai family businesses say that improving digital capabilities is a business priority, which is less than 44% of similar businesses globally.

References

Anchalikasite. (2017, October 14, 2017). Digitalization? <https://anchalikakhanti.wordpress.com/2017/10/14/digitalization>

Ashwell, M. L. (2017). The digital transformation of intelligence analysis. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 24(3), 393-411. doi:10.1108/jfc-03-2017-0020

Boratyńska, K., Cieślik, E., Kacperska ,E., Łukasiewicz, K., Milewska, A., *Gospodarka cyfrowa we współczesnym świecie – kraje V4*. Wydawnictwo SGGW, Warszawa 2021.

Davila, T., Epstein, M., & Shelton, R. (2014). *Making Innovation Work: How to Manage It, Measure It and Profit from It*.

El Sawy, O. A., Kræmmergaard, P., Amsinck, H., & Vinther, A. L. (2016). How LEGO Built the Foundations and Enterprise Capabilities for Digital Leadership. University of Minnesota.

Głód, G., & Głód, W. (2017). BARRIERS TO THE DEVELOPMENT. 42. doi:10.19253/rem.2017.04.003

WORKING PAPER

- Howard, E. (2018, September 5, 2018). The Evolution of the Industrial Ages: Industry to 4.0. <https://www.simio.com/blog/2018/09/05/evolution-industrial-ages-industry-1-0-4-0/>
- Jones, C., & Pimdee, P. (2017). Innovative ideas: Thailand 4.0 and the fourth industrial revolution. *Asian International Journal of Social Sciences*, 17, 4-35. doi:10.29139/aijss.20170101
- Khalid, K., Anjali, S., & Caroline, B. (2017). Technology budgets: From value preservation to value creation. Louangrath, P. (2017). *Thailand 4.0 Readiness*.
- Lee, V. (2014). Moving from digitization to digitalization. <https://www.i-scoop.eu/information-management/moving-digitization-digitalization/>
- Miller, D., Wright, M., Breton-Miller, I. L., & Scholes, L. (2014). *CMR Resources and Innovation in Family Businesses*. (Forthcoming, California Management).
- Patel, K., Patel, S., Scholar, P., & Salazar, C. (2016). *Internet of Things-IOT: Definition, Characteristics, Architecture, Enabling Technologies, Application & Future Challenges*.
- Pieriegud J. (2016). *Cyfryzacja gospodarki i społeczeństwa – wymiar globalny, europejski i krajowy*. [w:] (red.) Gajewski J., Paprocki W., Pieriegud J. *Cyfryzacja gospodarki i społeczeństwa – szanse i wyzwania dla sektorów infrastrukturalnych*. Publikacja Europejskiego Kongresu Finansowego, Instytut Badań nad Gospodarką Rynkową – Gdańska Akademia Bankowa, Gdańsk.
- Potter, P. (2018, August 06, 2019). Do You know how third parties really impact your business objectives? <https://www.rsa.com/en-us/blog/2019-08/do-you-know-how-third-parties-really-impact-your-business-objectives>
- ProcurementIQ. (2017). What is the Digital Transformation of Procurement Really About? <https://www.procurementiq.com/blog/digital-transformation-of-procurement/>
- Riahi, Y. (2018). Big Data and Big Data Analytics: Concepts, Types and Technologies. 5, 524-528. doi:10.21276/ijre.2018.5.9.5
- Vermeulen, F. (2018, January 11, 2018). The First Step Of Business Model Innovation. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/freekvermeulen/2018/01/11/the-first-step-of-business-model-innovation-focus/#2fe6bcf25022>
- Waller, G., & Aron, D. (2014). Taming the Digital Dragon. Gartner, Inc.
- Wiboonyasake, M. (2018). Industry 4.0 VS Thailand 4.0. Aware Group. <https://www.aware.co.th/thailand4-0/>
- Wu Hong, C. (2017). Family Businesses in the Digital Economy. KPMG Services Pte.Ltd.

Reports

- PwC's 11th Global Family Business Survey: Thailand Report. <https://www.pwc.com/th/en/services/EPB/family-business-survey-20...>
- Family-owned businesses: Leading in an evolving business ecosystem. <https://www2.deloitte.com/th/en/pages/deloitte-private/articles/family-owned-business.html>

